

CONJUNCTION CONTROL IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT - In Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), there are at least one sinks or base stations and numerous sensor nodes disseminated over wide region. Sensor nodes have confined power. Whenever a specific occasion is happened, these sensor nodes can send enormous volume of information towards the sink. It can bring about cradle flood at the nodes. It causes packet drops and furthermore network throughput diminishes. In WSNs, congestion might prompt energy squander because of countless retransmissions and packet drops. Thus it abbreviates the lifetime of sensor nodes. Along these lines, congestion in WSNs should be controlled to diminish the lost cause and furthermore to build the lifetime of sensor nodes. In this paper Proposed Enhanced Differed Reporting Rate algorithm (EDRR) congestion control components will further develop network throughput, packet conveyance proportion and packet misfortune. Many organization angles, for example, reporting rate, node density, packet size and so on can influence congestion. Congestion can constrain by use.

Keywords: [Wireless Sensor Networks, Congestion, Buffers, EDRR.]

1. INTRODUCTION

A wireless sensor organization (WSN) comprises of countless nodes, which have detecting, handling, and conveying capacities. Nodes in a WSN don't just screen their current circumstance, however they likewise forward and course information packets to at least one delegated sink nodes. It is realized that there are open issues that limit the pragmatic reception of WSNs. These constraints come from the way that every individual wireless node in a WSN has diminished handling capacities as well as restricted energy financial plan. Network congestion happens when the framework is near its conveying limit and an increment on the approaching traffic, or even a burst, may over-burden node cradles with a potential cascading type of influence that might transform into a calamity. On these circumstances, and except if a congestion control system is utilized, the quantity of packets showing up to their last end falls suddenly. Conversely, an organization under congestion control holds near an optimal reaction. That is, the active traffic approaches the organization conveying limit. Moreover, for WSN applications, congestion control instruments ought to likewise think about the results of wireless transmissions, like interference and power loss.

The progression in minimal expense, little, and minuscule sensor nodes causes a critical job where the sensor nodes to have exceptionally alluring qualities of detecting the ecological circumstances and interaction the got signals. The sensor nodes can be conveyed in all available and unavailable regions for detecting the information across different applications like war zone, building investigation, target field imaging nursery, and observing war zone. The sending of sensor nodes is application-subordinate, so it very well may be irregular or deterministic. The sensor nodes of the wireless sensor organization (WSN) sense the information or occasion, assemble the information under characterized infrastructure, and cycle they got signals. After a great deal of progression in wireless sensor networks, it is missing with not many details like restricted memory, deficient calculation, restricted data transmission, and battery powered nodes. Because of the short communication scope of sensor nodes, the middle of the road nodes collaborates in sending the information packets. There are different utilizations of WSN where sensor nodes are conveyed in an infrastructure-less organization. The sensor nodes sense an occasion and report to the closest base station for individual activity. To acquire the nature of service, for example, congestion-free start to finish information conveyance and delay-free information transmission, a successful and proficient organization is expected to plan to handle congestion and energy issues of WSN.

Congestion in wireless sensor network is made at two levels: link level congestion and node level congestion. As indicated by node level congestion, when rate of packet appearance is progressed than rate of packet service, it causes congestion. This kind of congestion occurs in most pieces of sensor nodes which are closer to the sink. Node level congestion grows packet loss and misuse of power in wireless sensor organization. In like manner, this kind of congestion straightforwardly influences accessibility of organization and lifetime of the organization. While, control of congestion contains two areas: 1. Congestion and interference location and 2. A rate control system, which changes the rate of reporting. Different measurements are used as a section for congestion discovery, for instance, station load, packet service time, packet entomb appearance time, support length and so on. Congestion control and counteraction contain measures taken for controlling the traffic inside the framework and furthermore maintains a strategic distance from breakdown in congestion. An integrated Congestion Control approach

can't be ordinarily applied since it prompts a few significant downsides. At first, such methodology accelerates over-burden of unnecessary communication in the framework which rapidly depletes the batteries. Besides, unified choice is made for congestion control which results in sluggish response to change in rush hour gridlock and organization condition. Then again, a methodology which doesn't use the in network the board limit of wireless sensor network permits simple handling and individual node direction. At last, in the event of correspondence disappointment, the whole framework will be in functional.

2. EXISTING METHODOLOGY

1. Dongho et.al proposed ADCC protocol by is a congestion control scheme for the WSN based home automation and is similarly valuable to general sensor network in view of the obligation cycle change of the sensor gadgets. The ADCC protocol controls the congestion in light of asset control plan, and traffic signal plan. The ADCC protocol occasionally computes the service time by monitoring the approaching packets at MAC level to distinguish congestion. At the point when congestion degree lies underneath the specific limit, the obligation cycle is acclimated to diminish the congestion. In the event that traffic is raised over the predefined edge, the sending rate of the asset is decreased. The ADCC protocol considers the cradle inhabitation and the link burden to recognize congestion. In any case, the single support inhabitation is inadequate to assess the right level of the congestion and is utilized for the locally situated automation.

2. Meera S. et al. proposed Congestion Control in wireless sensor networks using Prioritized Interface Queue (PIQ). Introduced double queue with control congestion utilizing cross layer approach a transitional node infers congestion control instrument to further develop the organization execution by decreasing the data sending rate to the downstream nodes. The intelligent routing selects the best node having low traffic to advance the packets. The intelligent routing is performed utilizing congestion information given by the sink. The adaptable queue is presented at the point of interaction of organization and MAC layer is presented where node generated traffic. The approaching traffic is separately positioned in the double queues. The separate threshold is indicated for both the queues. Whenever threshold emerges, the data from the packets queue are overwritten by the approaching traffic as packet drop punishment is higher than the drop punishment. Anyway this strategy may results in loss of target data in a circumstance where as of late sense data contain the target data, which will be overwritten by the approaching data. To control transient congestion when transient cradle spans to the threshold value it decreases the sending rate to the downstream nodes.

3. J. Jean Justus, A. Chandra Sekar et.al proposed Congestion control in wireless sensor network using hybrid epidemic and DAIPaS approach. Wireless sensor network is a dispersed system for sensing and monitoring the incorporated climate. For the most part congestion in WSN network happens because of transmission of packet in the unseemly path from source to objective. Congestion in network makes extra burden to the organization. In

Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) Congestion is one of the considered test which lessens the asset and number of nodes conveyed in the organization. For congestion control in WSN, there is a need to find and distinguish routing information about every node in the organization for compelling transmission path identification from source node to objective node. In this exploration, we propose a hybrid Dynamic Alternative Path Selection (DalPaS) approach for congestion control in WSN. Data total is finished by the node in the organization to diminish the congestion among the organization path in the organization. For execution assessment of the WSN hybrid epidemic algorithm is proposed.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Proposed congestion control protocol, Differed Reporting Rate (DRR) is to plan and execution of component to relieve congestion in WSNs by utilizing differed reporting rate control. Congestion Control component ought to be fair and energy-productive. There are three components that can manage this issue like Congestion detection, Congestion notification and Reporting rate changes.

Wireless Sensor Networks

Contains different wireless contraptions presented with various types of sensors to accumulate data from the environment and assembled data is given off from one sensor to another, using a multi-skip routing protocol towards the best goal, called sink. At the sink, information combination and examination happen. The sensor nodes are confined in battery force, memory, and getting ready limits. The place of various routing plans is to in a perfect world utilize the resources of WSN to achieve the most outrageous throughput.

Congestion Control

Congestion control is a basic zone inside wireless sensor networks (WSN), where traffic gets more conspicuous than the aggregated or individual constraint of the secret channels. Along these lines, exceptional considerations are expected to develop more perplexing procedures to avoid, distinguish, and resolve congestion. The obliged resources of the WSN ought to be considered while figuring out such methods to achieve the best throughput.

Buffer-based Congestion

Every node involves a buffer for the packets ready to be sent. The flood of this buffer causes congestion and packets loss. This is because of high reporting rate that changes in time because of dynamic channel conditions. The many-to-one nature (or unite cast) of WSNs causes congestion, notwithstanding different causes imparted to general wireless networks. It is shown that while utilizing huge buffer sizes, the organization load increment decisively hurts the occasion dependability, because of the restricted limit of the common wireless medium. Whenever buffer size is decreased, occasion unwavering quality can be improved somewhat. For low buffer size values, buffer floods lead to a bigger number of packet losses yet bring about lower channel conflict and lower start to finish packet dormancy values contrasted with those values of higher buffer sizes.

Congestion control mechanism uses Buffer

Occupancy as a technique for Congestion Detection and Congestion Control is performed by differed reporting rate changes. In the differed reporting rate change, sensor nodes which are close to sink are having minimum reporting rates and it continues expanding for the sensor nodes which are away from sink node.

Congestion Detection Algorithm

To detect the congestion in WSNs, following are the steps:

1. Monitor the buffer occupancy at each node constantly.
2. Consider that because of the approaching progression of the packets; buffer is filled up to currentpr, wherecurrentpr is the ongoing buffer occupancy.
3. If currentpr ≥ 80 , then set CN bit.
4. Send this choke packet to past nodes.
5. If past node receives step 4 choke packets, then it must decrease the stream rate.
6. If currentpr ≤ 60 , then reset CN bit.
7. If past node receives step 6 choke packets, past node might expand the stream rate.

Enhanced DRR (EDRR) Algorithm

Following steps involved in Enhanced Differed Reporting Rate method:

1. Find out number of bounces for example bounce include in the path from source to sink.
2. Estimate the reporting rate for every sensor node.
3. Set node close to sink reporting rate to minimum and it will increment as we disappear from sink node.
4. Each node is having reporting rate changes.

Adaptive Flow Rate Control (AFRC) Algorithm

After detection of congestion, subsequent stage is to estimate reporting rates for sensor nodes. To assess the reporting rate for every sensor node, Adaptive Flow rate control algorithm is utilized. It is as per the following:

- a) After getting the packet, on the off chance that congestion notification bit is set, the AFRC algorithm is executed for new flow rates (packets each second).
- b) Current queue length is recovered from the packets.
- c) New flow rates are determined by AFRC. The numerical model for flow control is, $y = 51.56 \ln(x) - 85.56$, where x = updated flow rate and y = current queue length.
- d) The output rate of a node is set with recently determined rate.
- e) New rate is kept up with until next congestion notification will be detected.

This result is opposite to the ordinary idea that restricted energy utilization in the organization. This property is profitable for continuous applications. The impact of most extreme retransmission limit albeit moderate expansion in this cutoff has a massive contrast with low retransmission values, the exhibition in congestion control reporting rates of each and every node.

4. EXISTING METHODOLOGY

1. Packet Delivery Ratio

No of Nodes	ADCC	DalPaS	Proposed EDRR
2	0.73	0.80	0.95
4	0.74	0.83	0.96
6	0.76	0.85	0.97
8	0.77	0.87	0.98
10	0.79	0.88	0.99

Table 1. Comparison of Packet Delivery Ratio

The table 1 Comparison of Packet Delivery Ratio values explain the different values of existing algorithms (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR. While comparing the Existing algorithm (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 0.73 to 0.79, 0.80 to 0.88 and proposed an EDRR value starts from 0.95 to 0.99.

Figure 1. Comparison of chart Packet Delivery Ratio

The figure 1 Comparison of Packet Delivery Ratio values explain the different values of existing algorithms (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR. X axis denote the Nodes mobility speed (m/s) and y axis denotes the Packet Delivery Ratio. While comparing the Existing algorithm (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 0.73 to 0.79, 0.80 to 0.88 and proposed an EDRR value starts from 0.95 to 0.99.

2. Energy Consumption

No of Nodes	ADCC	DalPaS	Proposed EDRR
2	0.73	0.80	0.95
4	0.74	0.83	0.96
6	0.76	0.85	0.97
8	0.77	0.87	0.98
10	0.79	0.88	0.99

Table 2. Comparison of Energy Consumption

The table 2 Comparison of Energy Consumption values explain the different values of existing algorithms (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR. While comparing the Existing algorithm (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 0.73 to 0.79, 0.80 to 0.88 and proposed an EDRR value starts from 0.95 to 0.99.

Figure 2. Comparison of chart Energy Consumption

The figure 2 Comparison of Energy Consumption values explain the different values of existing algorithms (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR. X axis denote the No of Nodes and y axis denotes the Energy Consumption. While comparing the Existing algorithm (ADCC, DalPaS) and proposed EDRR, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 0.73 to 0.79, 0.80 to 0.88 and proposed an EDRR value starts from 0.95 to 0.99.

CONCLUSION

Congestion in network makes extra load to the organization. In Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) Congestion is one of the considered tests which reduce the asset and number of nodes conveyed in the organization. Congestion in WSN causes packet loss, delay, energy consumption in the organization. Proposed work addresses the congestion control in WSNs. In this paper proposed method, congestion can be moderated utilizing Enhanced Differed Reporting Rate (EDRR) control. Henceforth, adaptive flow rate control is the strategy that can be utilized to control reporting rates of each and every node. The reproduction results show better execution as far as PDR and energy consumption by sensor nodes subsequent to applying EDRR algorithm.

REFERENCES

- [1]. L. Popa, C. Raiciu, I. Stoica and D. S. Rosenblum, "Reducing Congestion Effects in Wireless Networks by Multipath Routing," Proceedings of the 2006 IEEE International Conference on Network Protocols, Santa Barbara, CA, 2006, pp. 96-105, doi: 10.1109/ICNP.2006.320202.
- [2]. Mingwei Li and Yuanwei Jing, "Feedback congestion control protocol for wireless sensor networks," 2012 24th Chinese Control and Decision Conference (CCDC), Taiyuan, 2012, pp. 4217-4220, doi: 10.1109/CCDC.2012.6244675.
- [3]. S. Chen and N. Yang, Congestion avoidance based on lightweight buffer management in sensor networks, IEEE Trans. Parallel Distrib. Syst. vol.17, no.9, 2006, pp.934-946.
- [4]. R. Kumar, R. Crepaldi, H. Rowaihy and A. Harris, Mitigating performance degradation in congested sensor networks, IEEE TransMobile Compute., vol.7, no.6, 2008, pp.682-697.
- [5]. N. Thrimoorthy and Dr. T. Anuradha "A Review on Congestion control Mechanisms in Wireless Sensor Networks" N. Thrimoorthy Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Applications ISSN: 2248-9622, Vol. 4, Issue 11 (Version 2), November 2014, pp.54-59

[6]. A. Sharif, V. Potdar, and A. J. D. Rathnayaka, "Prioritizing Information for Achieving QoS Control in WSN," in Proc. of 24th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (AINA), April 2010, pp. 835-842.

[7]. M. O. Rahman, M. M. Monowar, B. G. Choi, and C. S. Hong, "An approach for congestion control in sensor network using priority based application," in Proc. of the 2nd international conference on Ubiquitous information management and communication, ICUIMC, 2008, pp. 430-435

[8]. A. Sridharan and B. Krishnamachari, "Explicit and precise rate control for wireless sensor networks," in Proc. of the 7th ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems, SenSys, November 4-6 2009, pp. 29-42.

[9]. X. Qiu, D. Ghosal, B. Mukherjee, J. Yick, and D. Li, "Priority Based Coverage-Aware Congestion Control for Multihop Wireless Sensor Networks," in Proc. of IEEE 28th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems Workshops, ICDCS, 2008, pp. 285-290.

[10]. J. Wan, M. Chen, F. Xia, D. Li, and K. Zhou, "From machine-to-machine communications towards cyber-physical systems," Computer Science and Information Systems, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1105-1128, Jun 2013.